

Mass, IR, UV and EPR spectral characterization of the complexes of $(\text{NPH}_2)_3$ with Cu^{II} compound

Yogendra Pal Singh and S. P. S. Jadon*

Department of Chemistry, S. V. College, Aligarh-202 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : sps_jadon@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 14 February 2008, revised 10 February 2009, accepted 12 March 2009

Abstract : Hexahydrocyclotriphosphazene (HHCTP) was refluxed with Cu^{II} acetate in chlorobenzene when two products, Cu^{IIA} and Cu^{IIB} were obtained. On the basis of their Mass, IR, UV and EPR spectral investigations, Cu^{IIA} and Cu^{IIB} complexes have been formulated as $(\text{P}_9\text{N}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{-Cu})$ and $(\text{P}_3\text{N}_3\text{H}_2\text{-Cu})_2$ respectively.

Keywords : Hexahydrocyclotriphosphazene (HHCTP), $(\text{NPH}_2)_3$, Cu^{II} acetate.

Introduction

Complexes of 1,3,5-hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene $(\text{NPCl}_2)_3$ with various transition metal ions have been reported¹. In the present paper we have reported the synthesis and characterization of two copper complexes with hexahydrocyclotriphosphazene.

Results and discussion

The green coloured complex, Cu^{IIA} , formed by the interaction of $(\text{NPH}_2)_3$ and Cu^{II} -acetate gives the analysis as : (observed %) N, 26.00; P, 57.78; H, 3.30; Cu, 13.11. The molecular weight of Cu^{IIA} is supported by mass line m/z 483 (M-1). Its mass pattern as observed in its mass spectra (Fig. 1a) and obtained by FAB fragmentation process, indicates mass lines at m/z 453, 426, 391, 343, 312, 279, 253, 219, 205, 167 and 124.

The complex Cu^{IIB} is brownish coloured solid decompose on heating has the composition as : (observed %) N, 20.94; P, 46.38; H, 0.997; Cu, 31.76 and molecular weight 401 g/mol, Cu^{IIB} has been assigned as $(\text{P}_3\text{N}_3\text{H}_2\text{-Cu})_2$.

The change of Cu^{IIA} to Cu^{IIB} confirmed by the appearance of a mass line at m/z 413 (M-1) in Cu^{IIA} which on losing one N-atom, gives $(\text{H}_2\text{P}_3\text{N}_3\text{-Cu})_2$, Cu^{IIB} as :

Molecular formula of Cu^{IIB} is also supported by mass fragmentation process, the prominent mass lines at m/z 400, 382, 325, 267, 201, 141 (Fig. 1b).

The formation of both complexes of Cu^{II} may be explained by the possible reactions :

The IR spectra (Fig. 2) of Cu^{IIA} and Cu^{IIB} complexes are compared to each other. IR spectrum of Cu^{IIA} consists a very weak and broad band at 669.4 cm^{-1} , a condensed vibrations at 771.2 cm^{-1} and broad doublet at 2272.9 cm^{-1} for H-P-N \rightarrow Cu group, while the frequencies at 1055.4 and 1159.1 cm^{-1} (d) are due to P-N ring. Other vibrations at 1354.8 , 1597.9 , 2341.2 and 2370.6 cm^{-1} for H-P-N bands and 2828.9 and 3429.7 cm^{-1} are due to $\delta\text{P}=\text{N}$ band. Its IR spectrum suggests the tetrahedral bonding of P_3N_3 ring with Cu^{2+} ions.

In Cu^{IIB} complex, IR frequencies at 621.7 , 776.4 , 2728.7 and 2916.7 (dwb) cm^{-1} are due to four P-N \rightarrow Cu bands. Vibrations at 535 (C) and 837.6 cm^{-1} are for

Fig. 1(a). Mass spectrum of complex Cu^{II}A.

Fig. 1(b). Mass spectrum of complex Cu^{II}B.

P-N ring. The assignments at 1355.3, 1590.1 and 2364.5 (d) cm^{-1} are for H-P-N bands. The remaining assignments are corresponding to $\delta\text{P}=\text{N}$ band. IR spectrum explain that two P_3N_3 rings are linked to two Cu^+ ions.

The bands at 200 nm for charged transfer transition and 332.54 nm for $d\pi\text{-}p\pi$ transition are found in UV

spectrum of Cu^{II}A complex, while third band in spite of two assignment at 200 and 332.8 nm in electronic spectrum of Cu^{II}B due to ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ transition has been observed. The charge transfer transition causing the ionic environment is supported by the values of frequency ratios and oscillator strength (Table 1).

Note

Fig. 2(a). IR spectrum of complex Cu^{II}A.

Fig. 2(b). IR spectrum of complex Cu^{II}B.

Three signals in EPR spectrum of Cu^{II}A, indicate its paramagnetic character while the absence of signal in EPR spectrum of Cu^{II}B suggest its diamagnetic character. The values of *g* for Cu^{II}A are found less than

two for the empty energy shells. The EPR spectrum of Cu^{II}A and Cu^{II}B explained that the bonding of Cu in both complexes is different. Cu^{II}A (Fig. 3a) consists Cu²⁺ state and while, Cu^{II}B has a metal-metal bond (Fig. 3b).

Table 1. UV spectra complex of Cu^{II}A and Cu^{II}B

Complex	Assigned band nm (cm ⁻¹)	Molar absorptivity (ε)	ν_1/ν_2	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	Oscillator strength ' f ' × 10 ⁻⁵	Band gap energy ΔE_g eV (ergs) × 10 ⁻¹²	Number of conducting electrons (Nc)
Cu ^{II} A	200.00 ν_1 C.T. (50000)	0.360	1.6627	1992.84	2.2539	1.235 (1.98)	8.5 × 10 ⁵
	332.54 ν_2 $d\pi-p\pi$ (30071.57)	0.184			0.1797		
Cu ^{II} B	200.00 ν_1 C.T. (50000)	1.950	1.664	1995.19	6.6755	1.237 (1.98)	8.48 × 10 ⁵
	332.80 ν_2 $d\pi-p\pi$ (30048.08)	0.325	1.194	488.83	0.1353	0.275 (0.485)	3.82 × 10 ⁶
	390.46 ν_3 ${}^2T_g-{}^2E_g$	0.395			0.2246		

Table 2. EPR spectral data of the complex Cu^{II}A

Sl. no	Magnetic field H ₀ (Gauss)	$g_x = g_y$	g_z	g_{av} (B.M.)	μ_{eff}	χ_a × 10 ⁻³ (e.s.u.)
1.	3925	1.568	1.8627	1.672	2.0964	1.813
2.	3980	1.5464	1.8828	1.666	2.0816	1.788
3.	4060	1.5160	1.9228	1.663	2.0729	1.773

Table 3. Relaxation time of splitted EPR peaks of Cu^{II}A
 $\omega_0 = 8964.66$ MHz, H₀ = 3200 Gauss

Sl. no.	Magnetic field	Frequencies H ₀ (Gauss)	$\Delta\omega = (\omega_1 - \omega_0)$ (MHz)	Relaxation time (T × 10 ⁻⁵)
1.	3890	10897.66	1933.00	2.274
2.	3920	10979.92	2015.26	2.220
3.	3980	11147.98	2183.32	2.140
4.	4010	11123.01	2267.35	2.100
5.	4060	11372.06	2407.40	2.038
6.	4080	11428.08	2463.42	2.050

Experimental

1,3,5-Hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene, (N₃PCl₂)₃ was prepared as described (*loc. cite*)². (NPH₂)₃ was synthesized by Na/C₂H₅OH reduction of (N₃PCl₂)₃. Complex of Cu^{II} compound with (NPH₂)₃ was prepared by refluxing 100 mg of Cu(CH₃COO)₂ and 100 mg of (NPH₂)₃ using chlorobenzene as solvent for 6 h. The light greenish product formed was separated, washed with chlorobenzene, ethanol and ether, dried and stored in vacuum desiccator.

Fig. 3(a). Structure of complex, Cu^{II}A, (P₉N₆H₁₆ → Cu).

Fig. 3(b). Structure of complex, Cu^{II}B, (N₃P₃H₂ → Cu)₂.

A portion of Cu^{II}A was left in air for few minutes when it changed to brownish coloured product Cu^{II}B. Both products were analyzed quantitatively and mass spectrometrically by recording their mass spectra on JEOL SX 102 (DA-6000) mass spectrometer using FAB technique. Perkin-Elmer, Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-15 spectrophotometer and Varian E-X-4 band (LNT) EPR spectrometer.

Note

Acknowledgement

Authors wish to express their thanks to Professor K. P. Madhusudanan, Director, CDRI, Lucknow and Chairman, SAIF, IIT, Chennai for providing instrumental facilities.

References

1. Fatma Kandmirli, *Phosphorous, Sulfur and Silicon and the*

Related Elements, 2003, **178**, 2331; S. P. S. Jadon, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2006, **18**, 20; 2003, **15**, 151; B. P. Baranwal, S. S. Das and Ummer Fauzia, *Res. J. Chem. Environ.*, 2001, **5**, 55; M. Biddlestone and R. A. Show, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 178; J. Schranz, L. Stah and R. Staples, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1493.

2. H. W. Roesky, K. V. Katti and G. M. Sheldrick, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 847.